

Diversity and Ethnobotanical study of Genus *Leucas* R.Br. in Marathwada Region, Maharashtra, India

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ABSTRACT

The genus *Leucas* R.Br. (Lamiaceae) comprises aromatic herbaceous plants distributed across tropical and subtropical regions. India harbors over 40 species, representing a significant center of diversity. The present study was undertaken to document the taxonomic diversity and ethnobotanical uses of *Leucas* species in the Marathwada region of Maharashtra. Extensive field surveys were conducted between 2023 and 2025 across eight districts. Plant specimens were collected, preserved, and identified using regional floras and taxonomic keys. Morphological characteristics including leaf shape, inflorescence type, calyx morphology, corolla structure, and nutlet characteristics were analyzed. Ethnobotanical data were gathered through consultation with local informants and traditional healers. Seven species were recorded: *L. cephalotes*, *L. stricta*, *L. wightiana*, *L. martinicensis*, *L. longifolia*, *L. clarkei*, and *L. nutans*. Among these, *L. cephalotes* and *L. martinicensis* were the most widely distributed, while *L. nutans* showed restricted occurrence. Ethnobotanical survey revealed that these species are traditionally used for treating fever, cough, digestive disorders, wounds, and skin infections. The study provides baseline taxonomic data for further ecological, pharmacological, and conservation studies on the genus *Leucas* in the semi-arid regions of Maharashtra.

Keywords: *Leucas*, Lamiaceae, Ethnobotany, Marathwada region, Plant diversity, Traditional medicine.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Leucas* R.Br. belongs to the family Lamiaceae and was first described by Robert Brown in 1810 (Cooke, 1967). The genus *Leucas* is among the plethora of ethnobotanical species with promising applications in traditional medicines to treat different ailments (Selahuddeen *et al.*, 2024). Species of the genus are distributed across tropical Africa, the Arabian Peninsula, South and Southeast Asia, and parts of Australia (Harley *et al.*, 2004; Hooker, 1885). Members of the genus are typically annual or perennial herbs characterized by quadrangular stems, opposite leaves, and whorled inflorescences known as verticillasters. The corolla is bilabiate, usually white or pale in colour, and the fruit consists of four nutlets enclosed in a persistent calyx (Mukerjee, 1940). In India, species of *Leucas* are widely distributed in dry open habitats, grasslands, wastelands, and agricultural fields (Singh

and Karthikeyan, 2000; Malik and Anand, 2014). The genus *Leucas* comprises at least 130 plant species distributed mainly in Africa and Eastern Asia, with nearly 63% of the *Leucas* species native to India, and the diversity increases towards the Southern parts of the country (Sunojkumar and Mathew, 2008; Selahuddeen *et al.*, 2024). Many species are well known for their medicinal properties and are used in traditional systems of medicine for treating fever, cough, inflammation, and snakebite (Das *et al.*, 2012).

The Marathwada region of Maharashtra is a semi-arid plateau characterized by diverse ecological habitats such as dry deciduous forests, scrublands, grasslands, and cultivated lands. Despite its botanical richness, detailed taxonomic documentation of *Leucas* species in this region remains limited (Naik, 1998; Sharma and Karthikeyan, 2000). The Lamiaceae family is one of the largest among dicotyledons, with many species being highly aromatic due to the presence of external glandular structures that produce volatile oils, which are important in pharmaceutical and fragrance industries (Sardar and Manik, 2017). Therefore, the present study aims to explore the diversity of *Leucas* species occurring in Marathwada and document their morphological and phenological characteristics.

Many species of this genus are traditionally used in indigenous medicine for the treatment of various ailments. In rural communities, different plant parts such as leaves, flowers, and aerial parts are commonly used for treating fever, cough, skin diseases, wounds, and digestive disorders (Chouhan and Singh, 2011; Das *et al.*, 2012). Studies on related Lamiaceae members have reported the presence of beneficial phytochemicals including alkaloids, tannins, saponins, glycosides, and carotenoids (Ulhe and Narkhede, 2013). These phytoconstituents contribute to the antioxidant, anti-microbial, analgesic, and anti-inflammatory properties observed in the genus (Srinivasan *et al.*, 2013; Ganesan *et al.*, 2014). Ethnobotanical knowledge associated with *Leucas* species reflects the long-standing relationship between local people and medicinal plants. The present study records ethnobotanical information on seven species of the genus *Leucas*.

1. Study Area

The Marathwada region is situated in central Maharashtra between 17°35'–20°40' N latitude and 74°40'–78°15' E longitude. The region consists of

eight districts: Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar, Jalna, Beed, Latur, Dharashiv, Nanded, Parbhani and Hingoli. The climate is semi-arid with annual rainfall ranging from 600–800 mm. Vegetation mainly consists of dry deciduous forests, scrublands, and agricultural ecosystems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Field surveys

Extensive field surveys were conducted during monsoon (June–September) and post-monsoon (October–December) seasons from 2023 to 2025 across all eight districts of Marathwada region.

Collection and preservation

Plant specimens were collected during flowering and fruiting stages. Specimens were pressed, dried, mounted on herbarium sheets, and deposited in the BAMU Herbarium, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar (Accession numbers – 00961, 00962, 00963, 00964 & 00965). From each site 4 to 6 plant specimens were collected.

Identification

Identification was carried out using regional floras (Naik, 1998) and authenticated by experts at Department of Botany, BAMU and Deogiri College, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar.

Ethnobotanical Data Collection

Information regarding the medicinal uses of *Leucas* species was collected through face-to-face interviews with local traditional healers (locally called "Baida" or "Vaidyas") and elderly knowledgeable informants (Sawane *et al.*, 2020). A total of five practitioners above 60 years of age from Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar, Beed, and Latur districts were consulted. During interviews, local names, plant parts used, modes of preparation, administration routes, and ailments treated were recorded following standard ethnobotanical methods (Kamble *et al.*, 2014). The gathered data was verified through repeated questioning in different seasons.

Species Descriptions

Leucas cephalotes (Roth) Spreng.

An erect, hairy herb reaching 40–90 cm in height. Stems bear short and spreading hairs. Leaves are broadly elliptic to ovate with serrated margins and

short petioles. Flowers occur in dense, terminal globose whorls with conspicuous bracts. Calyx tubular and slightly curved with small teeth. Corolla white with a woolly upper lip and a longer lower lip. Nutlets smooth and brownish.

Flowering and fruiting: August–November.

Habitat: Common in waste lands, hill slopes, and Agricultural fields.

***Leucas stricta* Benth.**

An erect herb reaching 15–30 cm in height with grooved and hairy stems. Leaves narrow, linear-oblong and rough on both sides. Flowers occur in solitary terminal whorls. Bracts narrow and spiny-tipped. Calyx tubular and ribbed with an oblique mouth. Corolla white with a woolly upper lip and longer lower lip. Nutlets smooth and brown.

Flowering and fruiting: July–November.

Habitat: Found on grassy hill slopes and gravelly ground.

***Leucas wightiana* Benth.**

An erect annual herb about 40–70 cm tall. flowers in axillary and terminal whorls close together, Calyx tubular, teeth short, Corolla white with the lower lip longer than the upper. Nutlets small and trigonous. Nutlets oblong, dark brown.

Flowering and fruiting: August–February.

Habitat: Agriculture lands

***Leucas martinicensis* (Jacq.) R.Br.**

An erect annual herb about 1 m tall with quadrangular hairy stems. Leaves broadly ovate with serrated margins and short petioles. Flowers arranged in dense axillary globose whorls. Calyx tubular with several teeth and a strongly oblique mouth. Corolla white with the lower lip longer than the upper. Nutlets small and trigonous.

Flowering and fruiting: August–February.

Habitat: Very common on waste lands and Roadsides

***Leucas longifolia* Benth.**

A rigid herb growing up to 30–60 cm tall. Stems are branched above the base. Leaves are narrow, linear-lanceolate with thick margins and covered with stiff hairs. Flowers appear in axillary whorls forming spike-like clusters. Calyx short and ribbed with small spines. Corolla white and slightly hairy inside. Nutlets trigonous and dark brown.

Flowering and fruiting: September–November.

Habitat: Common on Roadsides and hill tops.

***Leucas clarkei* Hook.f.**

An erect herb about 15–30 cm tall with branched, grooved stems covered by long hairs. Leaves are narrow, lanceolate and slightly hairy. Flowers are arranged in terminal whorls with narrow bracts. Calyx tubular with slender teeth and villous mouth. Corolla white with a woolly upper lip and longer lower lip. Nutlets small, smooth and dull brown.

Flowering and fruiting: September–November.

Habitat: Found in rocky places and waste areas

***Leucas nutans* (Roth) Spreng.**

A small diffuse herb, usually 10–30 cm tall. Leaves oblong-lanceolate, slightly serrate and gland-dotted. Flowers are sessile in dense axillary and terminal whorls. Floral bracts narrow with spiny tips. Calyx strongly ribbed with unequal teeth. Corolla white with a woolly upper lip and longer lower lip. Nutlets small and oblong.

Flowering and fruiting: July–November.

Habitat: Rare, found near hill slope

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A total of seven species of the genus *Leucas* were recorded during field surveys conducted across the Marathwada region of Maharashtra between 2023 and 2025. The documented species were *Leucas cephalotes* (Roth) Spreng., *L. stricta* Benth., *L. wightiana* Benth., *L. martinicensis* (Jacq.) R.Br., *L. longifolia* Benth., *L. clarkei* Hook.f., and *L. nutans* (Roth) Spreng.

Among the recorded species, *L. cephalotes* and *L. martinicensis* were the most abundant and widely distributed throughout the study area. These species were frequently observed in cultivated fields, roadside habitats, wastelands, and other disturbed environments. In contrast, *L. nutans* exhibited a restricted distribution and was recorded only from a few localities during the survey period.

The remaining species, namely *L. stricta*, *L. wightiana*, *L. longifolia*, and *L. clarkei*, showed moderate distribution and were mainly confined to grasslands, dry scrub vegetation, rocky slopes, and open habitats. Most species flowered and fruited during the monsoon and post-monsoon seasons (July–November), although *L. wightiana* and *L. martinicensis* continued flowering up to February.

Table. Ethnobotanical Uses

Sr. No.	Species	Plant Part Used	Traditional / Ethnobotanical Uses
1	<i>Leucas cephalotes</i> (Roth) Spreng.	Leaves, flowers, whole plant	Used in traditional medicine for treatment of fever, cough, cold, diarrhea, and skin infections. Leaf paste is applied on wounds and headaches, while flower decoction is used for respiratory ailments. (Das <i>et al.</i> , 2012).
2	<i>Leucas martinicensis</i> (Jacq.) R.Br.	Leaves, aerial parts	Traditionally used for gastrointestinal disorders such as diarrhea and dysentery. Plant infusion is also used for malaria, eye diseases, and inflammatory conditions (Chouhan and Singh, 2011; Selahuddeen <i>et al.</i> , 2024).
3	<i>Leucas stricta</i> Benth.	Leaves, whole plant	Leaves are crushed and applied to wounds and swellings. Decoction of aerial parts is used to relieve fever, digestive problems, and respiratory diseases.
4	<i>Leucas longifolia</i> Benth.	Leaves, aerial parts	Used in folk medicine for skin diseases, insect bites, and fever. Plant extracts are also taken to relieve digestive disturbances and mild infections.
5	<i>Leucas nutans</i> (Roth) Spreng.	Whole plant	Traditional healers use this species for cough, fever, and inflammatory conditions. Paste of plant parts is applied externally to treat wounds and skin eruptions.
6	<i>Leucas wightiana</i> (Wall. ex Benth.)	Leaves, roots	Leaves are used in rheumatic pain and inflammation. Poultice of plant material is applied externally to reduce swelling and joint pain.
7	<i>Leucas clarkei</i> Hook.f.	Whole plant	Ethnomedicinal uses include treatment of fever, respiratory disorders, and skin infections. The plant is also applied externally for wound healing in some traditional practices.

Photo plate - (a) *L. cephalotes*, (b) *L. martinicensis*, (c) *L. stricta*, (d) *L. longifolia*, (e) *L. nutans*, (f) *L. wightiana*, (g) *L. clarkei*

The ethnobotanical survey revealed extensive traditional utilization of genus *Leucas* species by local communities. Leaves, flowers, roots, aerial parts, and whole plants were used for medicinal purposes. The documented species were commonly employed in the treatment of fever, cough, cold, digestive disorders, wounds, skin infections, inflammatory conditions, and respiratory ailments. Studies on related Lamiaceae members have confirmed the presence of aromatic phyto-constituents including alkaloids, tannins, saponins, and glycosides that contribute to these therapeutic properties (Ulhe and Narkhede, 2013; Sardar and Manik, 2017). Plant extracts from the family have demonstrated antioxidant, anti-microbial, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, anti-diarrheal, and hepato-protective activities (Srinivasan *et al.*, 2013; Ganesan *et al.*, 2014; Selahuddeen *et al.*, 2024).

Among the recorded species, *L. cephalotes* and *L. martinicensis* possessed the widest range of traditional applications, whereas *L. stricta*, *L. longifolia*, and *L. nutans* were primarily used for wound healing and skin-related disorders. The use of Lamiaceae members for skin ailments is well-documented, with various species reported to treat scabies, ringworm, eczema, and wounds (Tayade and Pathak, 2020). *L. wightiana* and *L. clarkei* were frequently used for relieving pain, inflammation, and fever. The ethnopharmacological use of related species for anti-inflammatory and anti-gout remedies has been previously reported (Selahuddeen *et al.*, 2024).

DISCUSSION

The present study highlights the diversity and distribution of seven species of *Leucas* in the Marathwada region, emphasizing their ecological adaptability and ethnobotanical significance. The widespread occurrence of *L. cephalotes* and *L. martinicensis* in cultivated lands, roadsides, and other disturbed habitats indicates their broad ecological tolerance and ability to thrive under semi-arid environmental conditions. Similar observations have been reported from other parts of India, where these species are recognized as common components of open and disturbed vegetation (Singh and Karthikeyan, 2000; Naik, 1998). The high species diversity of *Leucas* in the study area aligns with the understanding that the genus is native to India with increasing diversity towards the Southern parts of the country (Kumar and Mathew, 2008; Selahuddeen *et*

al., 2024). The restricted occurrence of *L. nutans* suggests that the species may possess specific habitat requirements and limited ecological amplitude. Factors such as soil characteristics, moisture availability, habitat disturbance, and interspecific competition may influence its distribution. Further ecological studies are necessary to understand the factors governing its occurrence and to evaluate its conservation status within the region. The concentration of flowering and fruiting during the monsoon and post-monsoon seasons demonstrates the strong influence of rainfall and soil moisture on the growth and reproductive biology of *Leucas* species. Seasonal synchronization of flowering with favorable environmental conditions likely enhances pollination success and seed production.

The ethnobotanical information documented in the present study confirms the importance of *Leucas* species in traditional healthcare systems. The wide spread use of these plants for treating fever, respiratory ailments, digestive disorders, wounds, and skin diseases supports earlier reports on the medicinal value of the genus (Chouhan and Singh, 2011; Das *et al.*, 2012; Ganesan *et al.*, 2014). In the context of Maharashtra's tribal regions, similar dependence on medicinal plants has been documented, where over 45 plant species from 29 families are used to treat gastrointestinal problems, fever, cough, skin diseases, and other common ailments (Sawane *et al.*, 2020). Traditional herbal healers in northern and western Maharashtra have also been reported to use indigenous plants for various therapeutic purposes (Kamble *et al.*, 2014).

Studies have reported the presence of beneficial chemical constituents in Lamiaceae species, including flavonoids, phenols, tannins, and alkaloids, that are substantial to the genus's pharmacological activities (Ulhe and Narkhede, 2013). The leaves of Lamiaceae members have shown high concentrations of alkaloids, tannins, saponins, and aromatic oils, which are widely used in Ayurvedic traditional medicinal systems (Ulhe and Narkhede, 2013). The essential oils and aromatic compounds from Lamiaceae species have demonstrated significant fungitoxic properties and are important in pharmaceutical and fragrance industries (Sardar and Manik, 2017).

The extensive utilization of *L. cephalotes* and *L. martinicensis* may be attributed to their wider availability and recognized therapeutic properties among

local communities. Documentation of such traditional knowledge is important for preserving indigenous healthcare practices and may provide valuable leads for future phytochemical and pharmacological investigations. Insight into the pharmacological activities of the genus includes anthelmintic, anti-microbial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-diarrheal, anti-diabetic, anti-nociceptive, and hepatoprotective activities (Srinivasan *et al.*, 2013; Ganesan *et al.*, 2014; Selahuddeen *et al.*, 2024).

Overall, the findings demonstrate that *Leucas* species represent an important component of the floristic diversity and traditional medicinal heritage of the Marathwada region. Continued taxonomic, ecological, and pharmacological studies are required to promote their sustainable utilization and conservation

CONCLUSION

The present study provides a comprehensive taxonomic account of *Leucas* species occurring in the Marathwada region. Seven species were recorded during field surveys. Morphological characteristics and phenological observations were documented to facilitate species identification. The findings contribute to the floristic knowledge of the region and provide a foundation for further ecological, ethnobotanical, pharmacological, and conservation studies.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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